

FLEX-SCALE: A Disruptive Approach Towards Flexibly Scalable Energy Efficient Networking

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Abstract— The European FLEX-SCALE project advances disruptive research on complementary optical x-haul network technologies in support of emerging requirements for 6G cellular systems. Employing a top-down strategy, it addresses the diverse requisites across all network levels. The architecture introduces Optical Nodes (ONs) for efficiently aggregating traffic, strategically placed to meet ultra-low latency demands at the network edge and varied capacities in the core. Utilizing optical Ultra-WideBand (UWB) and Space Division Multiplexing (SDM) multiplexed transmission links, each ON routes traffic at multiple granularities (MG), from full fiber to flexibly defined bands, down to individual wavelength channels, as needed by the traffic flows. This enables the replacement of electronic routers by all-optical switches, significantly reducing the energy consumption. The support of UWB/SDM boosts the network node aggregate capacity to 10 Pb/s, meeting the envisioned year-2030 capacity targets for 6G. With enabling technologies and components like the optical digital to analog converter (oDAC), the plasmonic transceivers, or multi-granular optical nodes; FLEX-SCALE seeks to make a reality key 6G network attributes like ultra-high capacity, flexibility, scalability, cost-effectiveness, low latency and reliability. A sophisticated control and orchestration system ensures optimal operation, energy efficiency and service provisioning, utilizing advanced traffic engineering, cloud-native architecture and machine learning. In summary, FLEX-SCALE represents a visionary and comprehensive approach, ushering in a transformative era for 6G connectivity.

Index Terms—Optical Xhaul network, Optical Fiber Communication, Software Defined Network

I. INTRODUCTION

THE arrival of the 6G network era ushers in technologies covering different network segments spanning from the Radio Access Network (RAN) to the core network. Addressing the diverse traffic demands and service requirements of 6G entails a comprehensive architectural framework [1, 2]. A critical aspect of 6G is the expansive integration of machine learning (ML) and artificial intelligence (AI), which demands the timely exchange of significant amounts of data to maintain the freshness of generated insights. Future optical transport networks are expected to play a crucial role in optimizing the Age of Information (AoI) metric, particularly as it pertains to ML/AI applications in 6G [2]. Pursuing these goals, FLEX-SCALE introduces innovative hardware and operating tools for optimizing the backhaul network's energy efficiency and cost.

Employing a top-down approach, FLEX-SCALE satisfies requirements across service, system/network and

physical/component levels. The architectural underpinning of FLEX-SCALE begins with Optical Nodes (ONs), acting as traffic aggregators from the RAN to the transport network.

ONs placed at the network's edge, catering to ultra-low latency services, require rapid switching capabilities, albeit with relatively smaller capacities [1]. In contrast, core network ONs route and switch data traffic carried over different multiplexing techniques, combining spectral (Ultra-Wideband - UWB) and spatial multiplexing (Space Division Multiplexing - SDM), enabling flexible switching at varying granularities from full fiber traffic, to bands, and down to wavelength services. This multi-granular optical switch node (MG-ON) not only reduces router demands, but also energy consumption and cost, entailing a significant leap in efficiency.

The proposed architectural framework exhibits scalability, envisaging link capacities scaling to at least 1 Pb/s and overall node throughput reaching 10 Pb/s or higher. FLEX-SCALE's UWB/SDM transmission and switching elements pave the way for enhanced transport capacity, with adaptable modulation formats to meet specific service demands.

Key requisites in optical networks encompass high capacity, adaptability to diverse traffic types, scalability, cost-effectiveness, and low latency with high reliability. FLEX-SCALE's core innovations include an all-optical digital-to-analog converter (oDAC)-based transceiver, MG-ON, and autonomous network control, to achieve 6G requirements.

The subsequent sections detail the MG-ON, UWB/SDM transceivers and the sophisticated control, monitoring, and streaming telemetry system devised by FLEX-SCALE. These advancements in terms of high-capacity transmission, efficiency, and adaptability, are poised to redefine how 6G optical transport networks are conceived.

II. FLEX-SCALE ARCHITECTURE (OPTICAL TRANSPORT NETWORK CONCEPT AND REQUIREMENTS)

FLEX-SCALE classifies the 6G services into seven categories based on three service level requirements: *latency*, *bitrate*, and *connectivity/density*; each category requiring one, two or all three requirements to be met in order to satisfy the target level of Quality of Service (QoS). The seven categories are: a) high bitrate broadband connections for quantum computing, holographic-type communications and flying networks, b) full fiber coverage and massive/dense fiber connections for digital participation, safe cyber-physical world and hazard monitoring, c) very low latency for AI-aided decisions and intelligent

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machines, d) high bitrate and massive/dense fiber connections for ultra-smart city and Augmented Reality (AR)-aided education, e) high bitrate and low latency for Metaverse, aerospace navigation and telesurgery, f) massive/dense fiber connections and low latency, for IoT industrial devices and collaborative robots, g) full fiber coverage and massive/dense fiber connections, high bitrate and low latency for ultra-smart transportation, digital twin and fully autonomous driving.

In fact, target use cases of FLEX-SCALE technology include the transport through a metro and national network of futuristic residential entertainment services [3] featuring systems/data rates ranging from head-mounted devices (~ 100 Mb/s) and lenslet light-field 3D (naked eye) (~ 1 Gb/s) to true hologram (naked eye) (~ 1 Tb/s), requiring sub-millisecond to 7 millisecond latencies. Traffic assumptions include an average use of 30 minutes per day for 1% of households in the target reference topology [4]. In the same traffic requirement scale, the use case of 6G connectivity provision by operators is regarded a vital goal, featuring end-user 1 Gb/s-data-rates with 1 Tb/s backhaul peaks.

These use cases call for a fully flexible ultra-high-speed network capable of moving the transmission and switching capacity throughout the network at a new scale of traffic hierarchy. The entire system/network place their emphasis on the provisioning of a) traffic flows achieving a 50% reduction of energy consumption, b) traffic flows delivered in less than $15\mu\text{s}$, considering packet and optical layers, c) spectral and spatial optical channels at 10 Tb/s, and d) achieving network reconfiguration in 10 μs .

FLEX-SCALE envisions a centralized network with a limited number of interconnection points to the Internet, to which large volumes of traffic are directed. A high-level schematic of the network is presented in Fig. 1. Optical grooming in MG-ONs, configured in Route-and-Select topologies and supporting colorless-directionless-

contentionless (C/D/C) operation, allows optimal bypassing of intermediate energy-hungry packet nodes, leading to a reduction in router capacity and port count. A good candidate packet node for bypassing is the metro-backbone interconnect (HL3 level, as per Telefónica's IP hierarchy [5]), facilitating metro-backbone convergence and transparent transport from metro-aggregation nodes (HL4) —arranged in horseshoe structures hubbed to two HL3 nodes— all the way to nodes hosting content origin servers/CDN caching (HL2), as well as to the internet peering points (HL1). MG-ONs enable switching at different granularities, from wavelength channel switching (≥ 50 GHz), through flexible waveband switching (1-8 THz)—enabled by the flexibly configurable waveband-selective switches (WBSS) developed in FLEX-SCALE—to full fiber switching (spanning the S+C+L optical communication bands, ~ 21 THz), in support of optical interfaces from hundreds of Gb/s to many 10's Tb/s per spectral/spatial lane, and lane multiplexing techniques, such as UWB and SDM. This helps scale the link and node capacities to ≥ 1 Pb/s and ≥ 10 Pb/s, respectively, while providing flexibility to reduce cost/energy consumption. MG-ON configuration can be tailored to the needs of the heterogeneous segments and geographical areas that form a converged 6G network. Specifically, we envision UWB transmission, but not SDM, at the network edge, where several horseshoe structures hubbed to the same MG-ON share a pool of flexibly configurable bands enabling optical grooming into the different spatial lanes deployed in the backbone mesh. Wavelength channels added/dropped to/from each backbone node will be optically groomed to fill up wavebands that can be switched at the waveband level in subsequently traversed MG-ONs. Likewise, wavebands will be optically groomed to fill up fibers, which can be switched at the fiber level. Similar to what happens today with pass-through wavelength channels in ROADM nodes, some fibers and most wavebands will not

Figure 1: FLEX-SCALE framework's overview, which facilitates high-capacity transmission through the utilization of UWB+SDM and the development of: a) novel multi-granular optical nodes, b) ultra-high-speed transceivers equipped with energy-efficient oDACs, and c) an innovative autonomous SDN control system.

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require switching at the wavelength level. Based on preliminary evaluations, FLEX-SCALE targets traffic volumes in the order of 10 Tb/s at the metro aggregation nodes, assuming an average of 5-6 traversed links per connection and a traffic distribution that concentrates 90% of the traffic in 40% of the links. To accommodate this, 5-7 spatial lanes are required in the primary traffic routes, and up to 10 spatial lanes are necessary to avoid congestion in the busiest links, resulting in a total of 20-40 wavebands per link, which aligns closely with the state-of-the-art (40-48) \times 400G channels per link being deployed in today's backbone networks, thus establishing an equivalence between today's wavelength channels and the wavebands.

The transceiver technology leverages plasmonic modulators and oDACs, targeting ≥ 1 Tb/s per spectral/spatial lane and supporting the evolution to optoelectronic single-fiber, single-wavelength I/O interfaces of ≥ 10 Tb/s, with the operating wavelength freely selectable within the S-, C-, and L-bands. It also allows using multiple parallel lines to generate various combinations of spectral and spatial superchannels, targeting scalability towards 10 Tb/s net data rate (considering FEC 20% overhead) in 12 parallel channels, all while achieving a lower power consumption per bit (with a goal of 10 fJ/bit for dual polarization inphase and quadrature -IQ- modulation). The transceiver implementation integrates or can operate in conjunction with digital/all-optical spread-spectrum mechanisms to achieve stealth transmission (steganography) [6]. These techniques require all-optical, real-time decoding, thereby preventing digital post-processing and traffic analysis by an eavesdropper, while providing enhanced immunity against man-in-the-middle attacks and jamming.

Finally, to introduce efficient and dynamic allocation of network resources, FLEX-SCALE proposes an open, disaggregated 6G transport (packet/optical) network arranged in interconnected rings and mesh topologies enabling the inclusion of redundancy mechanisms, managed by autonomous SDN control, streaming telemetry and ML-enabled data analytics aiming to the highest reliability/availability.

III. MULTIGRANULAR OPTICAL NODE

The FLEX-SCALE MG-ON is a hierarchical network node that offers: (1) fast, route-and-select switching solution between ingress and egress ports at the flexibly-defined "band" level, going all the way to full fibre switching, implemented at the top tier; (2) support for full-band add/drop facilitated with an inter-band Optical Crossconnect (OXC) for C/D/C access; (3) single wavelength channel addressability at a secondary route-and-select architecture implemented using today's per band Wavelength Selective Switch (WSS) for backwards compatibility with legacy transmission schemes. The MG-ON can switch data at variable granularity for optimum cost/power consumption in a given network. It targets 12.5 fJ/bit energy consumption and enables flexibly defined bands from 1 Tb/s to multi-10's Tb/s per-band capacity with switching times of 10 μ s thanks to fast piezoelectric phase modulator technology.

The functional architecture of the node is shown in Fig. 2. At the top layer of the hierarchy (Full-fiber/bands – Layer 1) the optical layer performs either switching of the whole fiber (full-fiber switching) or that of multiple flexibly-defined bands (black lines from "West" to "East" and "South" direction), followed by spatial lane features. Also, a WBSS is placed on each ingress/egress fiber to enable route and select switching of flexibly-defined bands which can span from ~ 1 THz to full fiber, ~ 20 THz bandwidth. East/West and South links have an SDM dimension of 3 and 2 respectively, demonstrating the need for spatial lane changes due to incompatibly-wide links.

At the middle of the hierarchy of the node (Flexible Bands Access & Routing – Layer 2), we position an Inter-Band OXC which can add/drop up to four disjoint filtered bands and/or a portion of each of them across the UWB spectrum (blue lines linked to Inter-Band OXC, the rest lines are excluded for simplicity). The OXC allows any available transceiver resource to serve any direction in a contentionless and colorless fashion.

The node's lowest hierarchy (Layer 3) provides compatibility with legacy equipment using Intra-Band OXC and conventional WSSs for wavelength switching within each band (green lines to Inter-Band OXC). C-band is depicted as an example, but others (S- and L-bands) may co-exist.

To dynamically manage the traffic at the band level a new network element is introduced, called flex-WBSS. It offers dynamic reconfiguration at the optical layer, by incorporating flexible bandwidth allocation and a low-loss, fast-switching mechanism. As a result, high flexibility will be afforded onto the MG-ON through the effective use of the UWB wavelength range and offering reliable and low latency network reconfigurability with guaranteed service quality.

The flex-WBSS is able to process the input UWB optical bandwidth (1460-1625 nm, ~ 21 THz) and carve it into flexibly-defined, continuous and flat bands (as opposed to predefined bands in most multi-band transmission schemes). The above-mentioned adaptive filtering will be implemented using an optical lattice FIR filter structure (with ≥ 10 taps/weights) based on concatenated tunable Mach-Zehnder interferometers.

The carved bands, up to four being envisaged, are subsequently routed to multiple device output ports by a crossbar switch with $N \geq 19$ output ports (higher output switch

Figure 2: FLEX-SCALE's multi-granular, three-layered UWB/SDM-based Optical Node (MG-ON) architecture.

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port counts are possible with additional switching crossbar stages). Hence the WBSS is classified as a $1 \times N$ scale switch. The Flex-WBSS can also be operated in reverse, i.e., as an $N \times 1$ WBSS. Jointly, the WBSS is entrusted with band (or fiber) routing and selecting functions between optical node ingress and egress ports. The entire flex-WBSS is being designed and implemented as a photonic integrated circuit (PIC) utilizing silicon-nitride technology for low propagation losses through the programmable filter and switch.

Depending on the switching configuration of the crossbar element, the carved bands can also be sent to band drop (for full band detection or to be subdivided to wavelength channels). An OXC provides connection flexibility here. When whole fibers or multiple bands are switched from one direction to another and no add/drop traffic is present, the lattice filters can be set for pass-through mode (no filtering).

Fig. 3 depicts the flexible Spectral Band Switching paradigm, where the UWB input spectrum is carved to three out of four output bands: Band-1 is left empty; Band-2 is composed of the entire L-band and a portion of the C-band; Band-3 of the entire S-band; Band-4 of the remaining portion of the C-band.

First-order-lattice-type-filter-of-concatenated-MZI-like Structure

Figure 3: Internal structure of Flexible WaveBand Selective Switch.

IV. UWB/SDM TRANSCIEVERS

To support the ever-increasing capacities of data transmission, the FLEX-SCALE project aims to develop ultra-high-speed and energy-efficient transceivers. Conventional transmitters (Tx) can achieve rates up to 800 Gb/s by utilizing state-of-the-art high-order electronic “Digital to Analog Converters” (eDAC) and Mach-Zehnder-Modulators (MZMs). FLEX-SCALE aims to extend these rates to more than 1 Tb/s per lane by employing high-speed plasmonic modulators to achieve dissipation energies below 10 fJ/bit and developing novel sub-system designs such as “Optical Analog to Digital Converter” (oDAC) in the transmitter. Furthermore, the transceiver will cover the S-, C- and L-bands by using state-of-the-art plasmonic components. Employing plasmonic modulators enables operation with sub-Volt sources up to 500 GHz and beyond on a $10 \mu\text{m}^2$ footprint in complementary metal-oxide-semiconductor (CMOS) environment. Similarly, plasmonic detectors offer bandwidths in excess of 500 GHz [7] with no or

Figure 4: (a) Render of a transceiver. (b) Envisioned transceiver module packaging. Left: Module with RF connectors in the front left and optical connections in the back right. In the middle the photonic chip is mounted on a chip holder. Right: Zoom-in to the photonic integrated chip (PIC) showing fiber alignment grooves to the PIC.

little offset bias and high efficiencies.

On the transmitter side, the proposed novel sub-system will employ commercially available electronic low-power and low-order Pulse Amplitude Modulation (PAM), such as PAM2 and PAM4, drivers and plasmonic modulator structures consisting of either “segmented” MZMs or multiple plasmonic MZMs stacked in parallel that are biased and operated under certain conditions [8] to generate higher order (e.g., $m=8, 16$) optical PAM and Quadrature Amplitude Modulation (QAM) signal constellations as in [9]. This resulting sub-system design, called oDAC, achieves direct digital to optical translation of electronic bit-streams to optical PAM- m & m^2 -QAM signal constellations. oDACs can scale to 3.2 Tb/s and 6.4 Tb/s without requiring higher-baud rate electronics [10]. They can be classified into two broad sub-categories called “serial-oDAC” and “parallel-oDACs” and their merits have been presented with a particular focus on their advantages in terms of performance, energy efficiency, complexity and cost reduction compared to conventional commercially available implementations [8]. The essence of the oDAC advantages comes from the use of advanced photonics components over bandwidth-limited power-consuming electronics components.

In the framework of FLEX-SCALE, novel oDAC-based Tx PIC will be fabricated with the use of i) state-of-the-art PIC platforms, ii) plasmonic modulators and iii) commercially available electronic PAM2 & PAM4 drivers. The resulting Tx is envisioned to be reconfigured during operation (“on-the-fly”) to generate either multi-level PAM- m or m^2 -QAM signals with the best possible performance (as measured by the minimum symbol distance, error vector magnitude and bit error ratio).

As in the case of the transmitter, the receiver will be fabricated using plasmonic technology [11] and further enhanced with the incorporation of graphene allowing to transmit high data rates with small footprint. As an absorbing

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material, graphene was shown to be a promising choice [12], [13] and will be deployed in the photodetector. In [7] for example, it was demonstrated that plasmonic-enhanced graphene photodetectors can exceed bandwidths of >500 GHz, with a range of >200 nm optical bandwidth. Furthermore, high responsivities of >0.5 A/W were attained by using plasmonic structures to enhance the graphene-light interaction [13], [14].

Both transmitter and receiver can be realized on a Silicon On Insulator (SOI) chip, which allows them to cointegrate, making it easy to increase the number of components per chip. Through the local field enhancement explained in [15], high intensities can be achieved enabling good modulation efficiency over a broad range of wavelengths. Similarly, the absorption can be improved in the photodetectors by plasmonic structures. Due to the small footprint of these plasmonic devices, parasitic capacitances are kept low, paving the way towards highest bandwidth operation. In addition, the development of a monolithic plasmonic platform enables the fabrication of high-speed subsystems (e.g. oDAC) on a small footprint, realizing complex functionalities on top of the benefits of the SOI platform. Fig. 4 shows the envisioned transceiver module with electrical RF ports, optical connections and an integrated transceiver module holding its photonic-plasmonic circuits.

V. CONTROL, MONITORING AND STREAMING TELEMETRY

6G is expected to revolutionize the way we communicate and sense with promises of faster speeds, greater bandwidth, lower latency, and higher reliability. From a control and management perspective, it is essential to provide customers with end-to-end (E2E) 6G network services complying with negotiated Service Level Agreements (SLAs). This requires covering all different technological domains, such as the RAN, Core Network (CN) but also Transport Network (TN) as shown in Fig. 5. The 6G mobile operator could assign the resources depending on the requirements to meet, including radio, computing and transport network resources. Transport network services can be deployed between RAN network functions (i.e., fronthaul and midhaul), between CN network functions located at the edge and core computing infrastructure, or between RAN and CN network functions (i.e., backhaul). To this end, it is required to deploy an E2E transport software defined networking (SDN) control system that interfaces with the overall 6G management system.

FLEX-SCALE develops a novel multi-layer transport SDN control system for dynamic IP VNT management over MG-ON (WDM/WBDM/SDM) comprising a packet SDN controller for the IP layer and an optical SDN controller for the MG-ON layer, all managed by an E2E sustainable transport SDN orchestrator.

The sustainable transport SDN orchestrator is responsible for managing the overall network policies and routing rules for both the packet and optical layers, ensuring that the transport network operates optimally and energy-efficiently, while meeting the requirements of the 6G transport services. Reduction in energy consumption is a key attribute for future 6G transport networks. The optimization of energy consumption can be approached in different ways. Multi-layer (packet/optical) traffic engineering can be used to assign energy-efficient paths instead of the traditional maximum

Figure 5: Control of packet & optical transport networks for 6G

capacity-oriented optimization. Traditional IP layer is based on static virtual IP links between IP routers that are provided by statically configured optical channels. IP flows are routed hop-by-hop from HL4 to HL1 passing through HL3 and HL2. In the FLEX-SCALE approach, the IP SDN controller can monitor and optimize the IP network to autonomously trigger the provisioning of IP virtual links between pairs of IP routers. FLEX-SCALE targets energy consumption reduction by minimizing the number of hops in the packet layer and providing an optical bypass between pairs of source-destination IP routers. For example, HL4 routers can be dynamically connected directly to HL2 and (even) HL1, bypassing the power-hungry 3R regeneration performed in H3/HL2 routers. The multi-layer energy-efficient traffic engineering strategy can also be applied for daily traffic variations. For example, a detailed power consumption model of the network can enable to selectively switch off optical/IP network links under low utilization scenarios supporting energy efficiency. The target is to reduce the total network energy consumption, while maintaining a low blocking probability under dynamic traffic.

The autonomous multi-granular optical SDN controller is responsible for managing optical channels in the multi-granular optical network. It accounts for the evolution of next generation optical networks to support space dimension switching (SDM, e.g., through parallel fibers), optical-band switching (e.g., S-, C- and L-band division multiplexing), and WDM switching. The resource control of multi-granular optical nodes (MG-ON), combining wavelength, waveband, and spatial switching is very challenging since there is no previous work addressing all switching layers together. The Optical SDN controller, other than traditional wavelength Routing and Spectrum Assignment (RSA), supports dynamic optical band switching (FLEX-RSA), where an optical-band circuit can be dynamically configured to accommodate an increasing (or decreasing) number of wavelength channels (over the same path) depending on the traffic needs. The configuration, monitoring, and streaming telemetry of the multi-Pb/s optical nodes and the 10 Tb/s transponders developed in FLEX-SCALE is performed through NETCONF with augmented OpenConfig YANG data models. Recovery of the optical band, i.e., an entire band (e.g., C band) or a wide portion of it, is also considered. For example, in case of a C-band amplification malfunction, the optical band could

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be recovered over the S band along the same route, or in case of a soft-failure Quality of Transmission (QoT) degradation, the spectral window could be changed where QoT is superior.

The implementation of the FLEX-SCALE control and orchestration system relies on a cloud-native architecture such as ETSI TeraFlowSDN (TFS) controller. TFS is an open source cloud-native SDN controller able to scale the management of a large number of flows. Its modular architecture is based on microservices, using containers to isolate the functionalities of the components. Each microservice is independently deployed and communication between them occurs through an open interface based on Google Remote Procedure Call (gRPC). TFS has been extended with new or restructured microservices such as optical for multi-granular optical support, end-to-end orchestrator for packet/optical support, and a ZSM (Zero-touch network and Service Management)-aligned monitoring-analytics-automation loop. This enables to collect information of network services, operations, and devices in real-time, analyze data in real-time to detect any undesired conditions, and autonomously reconfigure/reoptimize packet and multi-granular optical networks based on the defined policies.

VI. DISCUSSION AND CONCLUSIONS

The FLEX-SCALE architecture for 6G optical transport networks offers a comprehensive and adaptable framework, addressing multiple network layers, from service and system requirements to physical and component needs.

The MG-ON is a key element, aggregating traffic from the RAN to the transport network, ensuring ultra-low latency demands for edge services and supporting varying capacity needs in the core network. In fact, it is an extension of actual nodes supporting 5G traffic, which are based on a route and select architecture that handles only wavelength division multiplexing which corresponds to one of the layers (Layer 3) of the MG-ON. The MG-ON enhances actual nodes by incorporating 2 additional layers for handling traffic in additional bands (UWB) and multiple fibers/cores (SDM). This layered design of MG-ONs ensures compatibility with existing infrastructure, facilitating their deployment in brownfield environments, as it is able to handle typical WDM networking.

As MG-ONs integrate UWB/SDM transmission and switching, the network can scale significantly, enabling link capacities of up to 1 Pb/s and node capacities exceeding 10 Pb/s.

To meet the stringent demands of 6G networks, we propose innovations like plasmonic-based transceivers (able to transmit up to 10 Tb/s); and the layered switching capabilities of MG-ONs. These advancements are in their early stages and first prototypes are expected in the short/mid-term. In fact, plasmonic technology is an area still under development, promising high speed/ density, small footprints and low cost.

The network operation is enhanced by a control and orchestration system that includes packet and optical SDN controllers, and a multi-layer SDN orchestrator. This system optimizes network operations and energy, to dynamically provision services across the packet and optical domains.

FLEX-SCALE layered WDM/UWB/SDM networking enables fine grained network slicing; allowing multiple logical networks to be operated as virtually independent business operations on a common physical infrastructure.

Incorporating cloud-native design and advanced machine learning-driven monitoring and automation, FLEX-SCALE ensures adaptability and autonomy, making it a transformative solution for the future of 6G optical transport networks.

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